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Reporting on CNRS R&D Cal/Val & metrology activities within QA4EO

Traceability for AERONET network &

Aerosol field campaigns validation & related Instrumental and Algorithm developments

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Content

1. Business As Usual Activity
2. Day time AERONET Europe AOD Traceability to WORCC/PMOD at OHP
3. Comparison NASA / CNRS / PMOD
4. Campaigns / Intensive Observation
5. Instruments and algorithm developments
6. Conclusion and planned actions for 2022-2025
7. Publications
8. Annex :
 - Annex 1 : Certificate of calibration (example)

Introduction

The main objectives of the work-package are called hereafter. The first main series of objectives in the frame of QA4EO are to contribute to the operation, QC & QA, maintenance and improvement of traceability of AERONET Europe calibration. LOA, in the frame of the Center for Aerosol Remote Sensing (CARS) ACTRIS central facility, is in charge of about 65 % of the European AERONET stations (35% for Spain). CNRS calibration facility operated by LOA is composed of two units, one located in Lille, a second and one complimentary at Observatoire de Haute Provence (OHP), South of France.

A second objective is to work towards the adaptation of existing data processing and aerosol retrievals to mobile observation, needed for satellite calibration/validation and exploratory platforms deployed during field campaigns. This is based on two new prototypes of an automatic mobile photometer developed in collaboration with CIMEL.

Campaigns involving photometer and lidar of potential interest for satellite Cal/Val realized and/or analyzed during Phase 1 are presented. The different outcomes expected to be delivered are compiled in this report, gathering all related materials presented in the different sections of this report.

1. Business As Usual Activity (AERONET/ACTRIS)

On average, LOA provides ~ 50 / year calibration services to European AERONET stations, in the frame of the ACTRIS infrastructure. Sun calibration platform is located, since early 2019, at Observatoire de Haute Provence (OHP), France. To this number, additional ~35 / year calibration services are provided at french level. The service was never closed, even during the COVID-lockdown. For redundancy purposes and for having rigorous AOD traceability with NASA, since 2019, LOA reference photometers are calibrated at NASA Mauna Loa calibration site. This is operational. During the QA4EO phase 1 period, new stations have been integrated in Europe (~15). At the same time, several stations operated a very old instrument and had the opportunity to purchase a new one. In the framework of ACTRIS implementation, all AERONET stations have to renew their instrument by 2025. Only CE318T models (the one that includes day and nighttime capabilities) are accepted. The CE318T model is also the model enabling mobile observation, at least on slow platforms like ships.

In the framework of ACTRIS implementation, 2 permanent positions have been obtained in France (LOA and OHP) to support the AERONET general activities, calibration and QC/QA. National and regional programs will support necessary multi-annual investment programs for LOA and OHP AERONET calibration platforms. During QA4EO-phase 1, ESA also contributed to the upgrade of these calibration platforms.

The data quality is also dependent on local site manager involvement. There are always stations with too low reactivity. The duty cycle on a given station is also affected by the lack of data during the recalibration phase. All stations included in ACTRIS perimeter (National facility and users) have been advised to solve this problem. For example, countries having several stations or NF would benefit from sharing at least one calibration kit (calibration spares) to maximize observation continuity. Another recurrent issue is shipping problems yielding delay in the calibration and reduction of the duty cycle (and lack of data). Especially

after the COVID-19, shipping companies became less reliable and few instruments were lost during transportation.

A last event to be mentioned is the contribution of AERONET to the COP26 in october 2021 (<https://www.actris.fr/aeronet-presente-a-la-cop26/>).

2. Day time AERONET Europe AOD Traceability to WORCC/PMOD at OHP

This activity has been proposed in the frame of QA4EO. This is a collaborative work with PMOD/WORCC, also a partner of QA4EO. In the frame of this collaboration, a PFR photometer has been set up, on a campaign mode, at the OHP sun calibration platform. Since CNRS/ACTRIS is expected to be a long-term activity, a PFR robot has been purchased and paid by ACTRIS-FR. Figure 1 is presenting a view of the OHP platform.

Figure 1: AERONET-LOA reference photometer at OHP together with GAW/PFR.

This first campaign has been successful. Collaborators from PMOD/WORCC have on their side developed a tool to visualize, in real time, the data and the difference between CNRS reference photometer and PFR. Examples are shown on figure 2.

Figure 2: Visualization of real time AOD comparison.

More details can be seen at <https://www.pmodwrc.ch/en/world-radiation-center-2/worcc/gaw-pfr/OHP/>.

A short report on this results has been published by ESA at the following site :

<https://earth.esa.int/eogateway/news/traceability-of-aeronet-europe-to-the-gawpfr-wmo-reference-for-aerosol-optical-depth>)

This is very relevant to inform european AERONET users about the comparability and traceability with GAW. Certificate of calibration delivered by CNRS has a specific mention, as it can be seen in the example given in annex 1.

More generally, this crucial activity and information are also part of the EURAMET/MAPP project (PI : J. Groebner) in which both CNRS and PMOD/WORCC are involved. On the metrology aspects, other projects are considered and of relevance for the general QA4EO objectives in MAPP. In very short, the other MAPP activities of interest for QA4EO are focusing on 1) an accurate laboratory measurement of CIMEL FOV, 2) on the development of a prototype led-based integrating sphere. These 2 points are extremely important to simplify and improve the calibration of CIMEL instruments in the network.

3. Comparison NASA / CNRS / PMOD

This activity has been started during phase 1 of QA4EO. CNRS reference photometers are now calibrated at Mauna Loa. Once calibrated by CNRS, reference instruments are shipped back to OHP in France for transferring AOD calibration to any field instrument. As explained in the previous section, CNRS reference instruments now operate beside a PFR instrument. This organization offers the opportunity to compare NASA reference instruments and CNRS reference instruments both calibrated, at the same time, at Mauna LOA. This regular exercise (every 3 months) is interesting because it brings traceability of NASA AOD to PFR/GAW through the CNRS reference instrument. It is important to note that for NASA and CNRS instruments, calibration of the 2 instruments is performed 1) at the same time, 2) with the same software, 3) following the same protocol, 4) but realized by 2 independent operators (1 at GSFC, 1 at CNRS). The following figure shows an example of results of the exercise.

Figure 3: Comparison between NASA and LOA reference instruments.

As stated above, these instruments have been calibrated at the same location, same time with the same centralized software but by 2 different expert operators. This exercise has been repeated several times in 2020 and the difference between AOD is lower than 0.001 (10^{-3}).

First comparison looks quite good, analysis under progress. This, regularly done, provides traceability of the whole AERONET to GAW/PFR. This information is now mentioned on

ACTRIS-CNRS Calibration Certificate. Calibration platform at OHP/Lille has been partly refreshed with 2 new Cimel robots in the frame of QA4EO.

In addition, the ACTRIS-Switzerland participation in the ACTRIS AERONET activity was recently validated (2021). PMOD/WORCC will receive regular national support to support this AOD traceability during the ACTRIS life.

4. Campaigns and intensive observation period

Networks of stationary instruments are quite a fundamental tool to provide dataset for satellite cal/val. Both column integrated and height-resolved (profile) properties are needed for assessing data and product quality of radiometric and profiler sensors onboard existing and coming Earth Observation missions.

Looking at the AERONET map which is the most dense worldwide network, very little data is available over the ocean. Efforts are currently made in that direction to enlarge the ground-based observation system over the ocean. Recent development is expected to enhance the capacity of the maritime component of AERONET (MAN) as well as the ACTRIS mobile exploratory platforms.

On the atmospheric profile point of view efforts are currently being made in the frame of ACTRIS, especially with lidar. In the frame of the ACTRIS implementation phase, efforts are made to upgrade and automatise existing multi-wavelength lidar. Another development direction is the design and operation of automatic compact mini-lidar that are easier to embark on mobile platforms like ship, airplane, car and train. In addition, both lidar types benefit from co-located automatic sun/sky photometers to enhance the retrieval of aerosol characteristics which is requested by space agencies for cal/val.

Efforts have therefore to be organized in several directions, i) instrumentation, ii) data QC, iii) on data processing, iv) on data inversion, v) on real time data and products delivery.

In the two following subsections, we summarize some of the main efforts supported during QA4EO phase 1 period for both mobile and stationary observation systems or platforms, in terms of campaigns. Data and aerosol products corresponding to these campaigns are available for cal/val activity. Some are in the AERONET database, others in the CNRS database.

4.1 Campaigns involving mobile platforms

The following campaigns have been either performed or analyzed or both in 2020 and 2021. We distinguished hereafter campaigns and permanent operation on mobile platforms. With respect to oceanic campaigns, we would like to mention CNRS participation in the MOSAIC (North Pole) on the German Polarstern vessel. However, quite a few night time data have been recorded due to unexpected technical problems not solved at that time. A second campaign around New Zealand (SEA2CLOUD) was organized in March 2020. Mobile photometer was pretty well working, however, due to COVID-19, the campaign was strongly shortened, finally producing a limited dataset.

- Short campaigns

- FIREX-AQ (USA-2019).

This campaign has been organized in Idaho (USA) during the fires season, in summer 2019. Climate change increases the frequency and intensity of fires in this region as we dramatically experience now every year. Impacts are so strong that all atmospheric levels can be affected, from the ground level with strong impact on the air quality as well as stratosphere since strong pyro-convection phenomena inject absorbing smoke layers in the upper troposphere, lower stratosphere (figure 4). The smoke plumes are then widely distributed, at least in the northern hemisphere, to Europe.

Figure 4 : FIREX campaign

CNRS participated in this campaign by performing at ground level mobile observations. Two mobile units were equipped with PLASMA (CNRS) and CE318T (CIMEL) photometers (both mobile versions), in addition to mini-automatic lidar (figure 5). At the same time the AERONET group set up a temporary regional network to increase the AERONET network density. CNRS objectives were to retrieve aerosols properties from mobile remote sensing data during FIREX-AQ campaign for studies of smoke transport from local to regional scale.

Figure 5: Mobile units equipped by CNRS during the FIREX-AQ campaign, deployed in the field to characterize smoke column and height-resolved properties

The following figure 6 shows examples of aerosol distribution during the William flat fires.

William Flats Fire (2019/08/04-09)

2019/08/05

Aqua/MODIS

3D Quicklook (RCS @532 nm)
DEM: SRTM 30m

Results shown with Oral Presentations at XI WLMLA and ELC 2021

Figure 6 : Case study of spatio-temporal aerosols monitoring. AOD data are available on the AERONET website (https://aeronet.gsfc.nasa.gov/new_web/DRAGON-FIREX-AO_2019.html) and lidar data at CNRS. Source: M.F Sanchez-Barrero (ELC, 2021).

- MOABAI (Beijing and North China Plain, 2017)

This campaign aimed at mapping at fine spatial scale of aerosol optical properties using a mobile laboratory equipped with a LIDAR, a sun photometer and in-situ instruments, performing measurements on-road. MOBAI was jointly organized by CNRS/LOA and LAGEO, Institute of Atmospheric Physics, Chinese Academy of Sciences, Beijing. The mobile campaign was conducted from 9 May to 19 May 2017 and had as main objective to map the pollutants distribution in Beijing and North China Plain (NCP) region.

The top of figure 7 shows the AOD distribution around Beijing, as revealed by observations. The highest AOD at 440 nm (1.34 and 1.9) were recorded during two heavy pollution episodes on 18 May and 19 May 2017, respectively. The lowest Planetary Boundary Layer (PBL) heights (0.5-1.5 km) were recorded during the heavy pollution events, correlated with the highest AOD and with southern winds. Transport of desert dust from Gobi Desert was captured during the mobile measurements, impacting Beijing during 9-13 May 2017.

Figure 7: AOD mapping in the Beijing city (top) and aerosol vertical distribution during NCP exploration (bottom). Source : Popovici et al., 2022).

Exploring the NCP outside Beijing (bottom of figure 7) provided datasets in regions with scarce ground measurements and allowed mapping high aerosol concentrations when passing by polluted cities in NCP (Baoding, Tianjin and Tangshan) and along the Binhai New Area.

For the first time, we provide mass concentration profiles from the synergy of lidar, sun photometer and in-situ measurements. The case study along the Binhai New Area revealed mean extinction coefficients of $0.14 \pm 0.10 \text{ km}^{-1}$ at 532 nm and mass concentration of $80 \pm 62 \text{ mg/m}^3$ in the PBL ($< 2 \text{ km}$). The highest extinction (0.56 km^{-1}) and mass concentrations (404 mg/m^3) were found in the industrial Binhai New Area. The PM_{10} and $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ fractions of the total mass concentration profiles were separated using the columnar size distribution derived from sun photometer measurements.

This study offers unique mobile datasets of aerosol optical properties in NCP for future applications such as satellite validation (figure 8) and air quality studies.

Figure 8: Comparison of day and night extinction profiles derived from CALIOP and ground-based mobile unit composed of photometer and automatic micro-LiDAR (MOABAI campaign, 2017, LOA).

- Permanent mobile operation
 - MAP-IO (Indian ocean)

A ship-borne photometer of CIMEL CE318T type was permanently installed in early January 2021 aboard the French research vessel Marion Dufresne in the frame of the MAP-IO (Marion Dufresne Atmospheric Program - Indian Ocean) research programme. The ship-borne version of CIMEL instrument has been developed by CNRS at LOA to enable measurement of atmospheric aerosols from mobile platforms, and to expand and automate the AERONET coverage to the vast ocean, an area which is currently manually operated within the Maritime Aerosol Network (MAN) branch of AERONET. The instrument is engaged mainly in the Southern Hemisphere/Indian Ocean to provide high frequency (3 min) Aerosol Optical Depth (AOD) and column-mean Ångström coefficient. Data is transmitted via satellite to CNRS/Lille where it is processed to produce spectral AOD, water vapor content, Ångström exponent and sky radiance.

(a)

(b)

Figure 9: (a) Overview of the ship-borne version of CIMEL CE318T on board Marion Dufresne and (b) example of AOD map during the SWING campaign, 2021.

The automatic AERONET compatible ship-borne CE318-T photometer contributes to satellite Cal/Val activities of current and upcoming Earth observation missions. Several research or commercial vessels are expected to be equipped in the coming years with this system to continuously measure and monitor aerosol properties over the oceans. A processing chain dedicated to mobile platforms is under development and will be implemented at the ACTRIS Data Center.

Figure 10: Example of day and night time AOD, Angström exponent and water vapor content during the MAYOBS campaign onboard Marion Dufresne vessel. http://loaphotons.univ-lille1.fr/photons/data_monitor/ship-data/maan.php

Figure 11: Day and night level 1.5 (QC) AOD time series measured on the Marion Dufresne, Sept. 2021.

The system will again be improved during the MAP-IO operation in the frame of AGORA-Lab, a joint partnership programme between CNRS-LOA and CIMEL SME. A future version could target radiance measurements from the ocean surface as well, possibly measuring water-leaving radiance. Integration of an automatic lidar system, ideal companion of photometer and in situ aerosol measurements, is planned to be tested in the future.

The first results has been published at Development of ship-photometer: permanent setup on Marion Dufresne (MAP-IO project), <https://earth.esa.int/eogateway/news/monitoring-aerosol-properties-in-the-indian-ocean>

The joint retrieval of spectral AOD and sky radiances is funded in the frame of several national and European programs such as ESA/IDEAS-QA4EO, AERONET, ACTRIS, Labex CaPPA.

4.2 Field campaigns (stationary)

This subsection relates campaigns organized at different geographical locations, respectively in China and in France both focusing on specific objectives and involving different instruments

- DAO campaign (China, Spring 2019)

First, we would like to cite briefly the DAO (Dust Aerosol Observation) campaign which was jointly organized in far West China by CNRS and CAS (Chinese Academy of Sciences), during Spring 2019 and focused on the retrievals of pure dust properties combining CNRS and CAS photometers, CNRS multi-wavelength lidar and chinese in situ data. This 2 months field campaign was located near Kashi city, West of China. This region is very weakly affected by local anthropogenic pollution, but by transported pollution and dust from surrounding arid and desert areas. The main results have been published (Hu et al., 2020). Such lidar data is extremely rare in this region. Lidar data are available from CNRS.

- COBIACC campaign (North of France, Summer 2019)

In the frame of regional programs (CLIMIBIO and CaPPA projects), the COBIACC campaign has been organized in the North of France, initially to study bio-aerosol and their precursors.

A rural site, located close to Caillouël-Crépigny small village has been equipped during 2 month (July/August 2019) with many remote sensing and in-situ gas and aerosol instrumentation. On the remote sensing side, an AERONET station has been set up as well as an automatic CE376 CIMEL lidar. Both instruments have worked perfectly during this period. The temporal variability of AOD at 500 nm and Angstrom Exponent (AE) computed between 440 and 870 nm measured by the sun photometer is presented in Fig. 12

Figure 12. Time series of AOD at 500 nm (green) and Angstrom Exponent (AE) computed between 440 and 870 nm (blue) measured by the sun photometer at COBIACC site from 17 June 2019 to 24 July 2019. The two heat waves periods, HW1 (23 June-31 June 2019) and HW2 (22 July-26 July 2019) are highlighted.

Figure 13. Time series of the LIDAR Range Corrected Signal (RCS) at 532 nm for the HW2 (22-26 July 2019). The maximum altitude depicted is 18 km.

Although the mean AOD recorded at Caillouël-Crépigny is moderate (0.17 ± 0.1 and 1.23 ± 0.37 , respectively), it is rather high for a rural site. This is partly explained by the long-range transport of Saharan dust in the free troposphere during the two heat waves, HW1 (23-30 June 2019) and HW2 (22-26 July 2019). The two heat waves are marked by a strong increase of the AOD and a decrease in the AE (Fig. 12), suggesting dust intrusion. The first dust intrusion occurred on 23 June 2019 and is also seen in the lidar data, showing aerosol layers up to 6 km altitude. The second dust intrusion occurred on 23 July 2019 and is presented in Fig. 13. During the two heat waves, the mean AOD at 500 nm were 0.21 ± 0.1 and 0.23 ± 0.11 for HW1 and HW2, respectively. With the arrival of dust over the measurement site, the AOD

then reached a maximum of 0.51 on 26 June 2019, 08:44 local time. For the HW2 the AOD increased from 0.11 ± 0.01 on 21 July 2019 to a maximum of 0.43 on 25 July at 08:30 local time. Figure 13 shows the lidar quicklooks of Range Corrected Signal (RCS) measured during the HW1 and HW2, respectively. The aerosol vertical variability was very complex over the two periods. For the HW1, the evolution of the Atmospheric Boundary Layer (ABL) during daytime is generally seen well delimited in the lidar data, up to 1-2 km altitude. Yet, the desert dust layers arriving at the site are seen descending into the ABL, contributing significantly to the aerosols measured at surface level. The aerosols up to 6 km altitude are most probably fine dust from the long-range transport. For the HW2, the ABL is also well delimited, up to 1.5 km altitude, and fine dust layers are present up to 6 km altitude. The same aerosol layer structure descending from 3 km altitude into the ABL is seen for the two dust intrusions, between 00:00 and 16:00 local time on 24 June 2019 during the HW1 and from 23 July, 19:00 to 24 July, 12:00 local time during the HW2. The arrival of these concentrated dust layers corresponds to the strong increase in AOD and decrease in AE. An interesting feature was also detected by lidar at high altitudes, aerosol layers in the 14.5-16.5 km altitude during the two periods. The arrival of thin aerosol layers in the lower stratosphere, at 15-16 km altitude, was first observed over Caillouël-Crépigny on 29 June 2019, afternoon until 30 June 2019, morning. According to Vaughan et al. (2020), these aerosols are probably smoke resulting from pyroconvection from wildfires over Canada and transported over Europe. For the HW2 we also observed aerosol layers in the lower stratosphere (14.5-16.5 km altitude). These stratospheric aerosol layers arrived in France following the eruption of the Raikoke volcano in the Kuril Islands on 22 June 2019, which sent ash and sulfur dioxide into the stratosphere. While ash was transported at the beginning of July following the Raikoke eruption, it is shown that small, non-depolarizing spherical sulphuric acid particles were observed at the end of July (Vaughan et al., 2020). Khaykin et al. (2020) also reported lidar measurements of the stratospheric layers over south of France. The stratospheric aerosol layers were observed over Caillouël-Crépigny during the COBIACC campaign, starting with 29 June 2019.

Dataset is available in the AERONET and ACTRIS-France databases.

- Fluorescence experimental campaign (ATOLL platform)

By the end of 2019, LOA started to experience new fluorescence detection with the LILAS Mie-Raman lidar in operation at the ATOLL platform in the frame of EARLINET/ACTRIS. Although not initially designed for measuring so small laser induced fluorescence, the first results look very promising to greatly enhance aerosol detection, typing and detailed characterisation, including when fluorescent particles are located within cloud layers. The atmospheric fluorescence emission is induced by UV laser excitation. The fluorescence is generated by particles composed of organic species. Therefore smoke, pollens and other bio-aerosols are strongly reacting to UV excitation. The current Lidar system is not designed to precisely measure this signal. However, time integration and focus on case study have shown the huge potential to improve aerosol remote techniques, hence the assessment of their impacts (direct and indirect). Since 2019, several papers have been published by LOA on these new developments. Both instrument development, data processing and aerosol retrievals are being investigated. The following figures provide one illustration of the new possibility offered. These figures correspond to the analysis of Californian smoke as observed from lidar time series acquired at the ATOLL platform.

Figure 14 gives an illustration of the hemispheric scale of smoke plumes released by Californian fires, as they are long-range transported and affected north of Europe and France.

Figure 14: Long-range smoke transport and impacts, from source to North Europe (ATOLL Platform). September 2020.

LILAS, the Mie-Raman-Fluorescence lidar in operation in Lille is a high performance lidar with a high level of automation which enabled the acquisition of this continuous time series presented in figure 15. Figure 15 focuses on the aerosol profiles measured on 11th of September 2020.

Figure 15: Detection, monitoring and characterization of aerosol combining Mie, Raman, Depolarization and fluorescence (source CNRS, 2021).

Figure 15 shows the extremely high variability in aerosol distribution observed in Lille during september 2021. Indeed, very complex atmospheric situations, characterized by mixtures of Saharan dust with Californian smoke, even with local pollution close to the ground, can be seen. The figure also illustrates the high level of fluorescence detected within the smoke layer, at around 6000 m. The figure also shows how the first combination of depolarisation and fluorescence can be used to type aerosol. Since depolarisation and fluorescence are almost direct lidar measurements, they can be obtained at high temporal and spatial resolutions which is helpful for the aerosol classification. The important consequence is that it will help to better determine the aerosol properties and then their impact on radiations and on the atmosphere thermodynamics and dynamics, as shown by figure 16.

Figure 16 : Impacts of stratospheric smoke on smoke layer stability and atmospheric temperature (Hu et al., 2021)

5. Instrumentations and algorithm developments

5.1 Development of mobile photometers.

For a long time CNRS has been cooperating with CIMEL in the framework of AERONET. By the end of 2020, the joint laboratory AGORA-Lab (<https://www.agora-lab.fr/>) has been created to foster innovation for atmospheric observation and monitoring purposes. The perimeter addressed is the photometer and lidar. Mobile aerosol monitoring systems are one direction of innovation. In previous IDEAS/QA4EO-Phase 1, CNRS/LOA development strategy with respect to mobile photometry has been presented. Two parallel directions are followed. These two directions are corresponding to photometers able to operate 1) on slow vectors (ship, vessel), 2) on fast vectors (airborne, cars, drones).

- Summary and current status of ship-photometer C318T

The first direction that has been validated during previous campaigns and very recently in MAP-IO (see section 4), is the adaptation of the existing CIMEL CE318T. New modules to measure head, pitch and roll have been developed as well as the communication of this information with the photometer. Sun and moon tracking have been validated. An important issue was the contamination of seaspray. This has been solved by creating an overpressure in the collimator to prevent any seaspray from entering and contaminating the front optics. The advantage of this approach is that it is 100% AERONET compatible. In summary, the many

characteristics of this CE318TM are 1) Track « reactive » sun/moon and sky measurement, 2) Attitude motion compensation, 3) speed measurement, 4) management sea sprays, 5) rain, wind, clouds detections, 6) Pressure et temperature, 7) Data acquisition and transmission.

Figure 17 : overview of CE318TM setup on Polar stern (source Yin et al., 2019)

Early 2022, this system can be considered as validated (TRL = 7-8 as it has been shown to be successfully operated in real environment conditions. Still there are possible improvements or simplifications for the setup on a ship that will be addressed in the coming period. The main issue and work still to be done, is more at the processing level (see section 5.4).

- Summary and current status of Advanced-PLASMA

The second direction is based on the PLASMA instrument developed by CNRS (Karol et al., 2013). This research prototype has been involved in many scientific missions. However, this instrument is not measuring night time AOD nor sky radiance. Moreover it is not waterproof and imposes a lot of flight constraints during campaigns.

We decided to develop a new robotization to support high speed, resisting rain and integrating a CIMEL CE318T photometer head since we target to remain 100% AERONET compatible.

A 3Dprinter prototype has been built by CNRS (figure 18) and is still under tests.

Figure 18: Overview of Advanced-PLASMA mobile photometer

In 2021, due to COVID-19 and Human *resources* limitations, the A-PLASMA project *slowed* down. Preliminary *comparisons* between CNRS reference photometer and A-PLASMA have been performed to optimize both mechanical and electronic components. Some raw signal comparisons are shown on figure 19 and were good for this first development stage.

Figure 19: Comparison between AERONET reference and A-PLASMA data (raw signal).
Check of the tracking capability (LOA, 2021)

The next phase and current phase we are in is to build an industrialized version and searching fundings to build a first small series of at least 5 instruments.

At national level, a new airplane (ANVOL project) dedicated to atmospheric research will be purchased in 2022. One A-PLASMA version is scheduled to be set up permanently on this airplane and will operate in an automatic mode, as soon as the airplane flies.

5.2 Development of innovating Lidar

In the frame of AGORA-Lab, lidar is also considered. The current need is to have more autonomous multi-wavelength lidar, lidar with new observation capability and also to have compact mobile lidar that could be setup alone somewhere on a mobile vector.

- Development of a compact automatic mini-lidar (CE376)

Several campaigns mentioned/illustrated in the previous sections involved such compact automatic micro-lidar. The new CIMEL micro-lidar (CE376) is a bi-wavelength (532/808), possibly measuring depolarisation at 532 as an option (current TRL is 6). The current effort being made for the 2-3 coming years, is to develop a quite robust (mechanical and thermally) version to be operated on various mobile supports. The goal is here to enhance the capacity of atmospheric research infrastructure in support of the space-based observing system and to extend spatial coverage of operations and completeness of existing observation platforms. Several projects (OBS4CLIM (on TGV), POLAR-POD (on fleet)) at national level have started for fostering these innovative technologies. A Ph.D thesis (2021-2024) is devoted to the “development of an autonomous integrated mobile system combining photometer and lidar to characterize and monitor aerosol properties”. A proposal is currently under preparation to answer an H2020/INFRA-TECH call on “mobile technology for atmospheric

monitoring” with the general objectives to provide new products and instrumentation, and to develop innovative technologies and more efficient and cheaper atmospheric monitoring equipment.

- Development of new Fluorescence LIDAR

The above-mentioned OBS4CLIM project (2021-2028) will support the design and construction, and operation of a new high power Mie-Raman-Fluorescence lidar for aerosols and cloud studies in Lille. This system called LIFE (Laser Induced Fluorescence Explorer) will be a research instrument, high-flexible, and very automated. It will be a companion of LILAS. This new instrument (PI : Q. Hu) is expected to be assembled by end 2022, early 2023. It will therefore be ready for contributing cal/val activity of the coming space-lidar missions (EarthCARE) as the LILAS data part of EARLINET database is contributing to AEOLUS Cal/Val efforts (figure 20).

Figure 20 : Example of contribution to AEOLUS cal/val. Data from ATOLL/LILAS UV data.

This future instrument will provide a more detailed fluorescence signature. LIFE high power UV laser will induce a much better measurable fluorescence emission and will also be more favorable for Cal/Val of EarthCare UV aerosol/cloud products. Specific data processing and aerosols & cloud retrieval will have to be designed and developed (see section 5.3). Early 2022, 3 Ph.D students are involved in this activity.

5.3 Data processing and retrieval algorithms development

In the framework of several projects, including IDEAS, QA4EO, ACTRIS, CNRS is developing advanced algorithms to retrieve aerosol properties from remote sensing data, e.g. photometer and lidar, and their synergy. Most of them are bringing added-value with respect to AERONET because they invert spectral AOD only to produce aerosol volume size distribution (Torres et al., 2017, 2021), or because the methodology is able to account for both photometer and lidar (GARLLIC, Lopatsin, 2013), BASIC (Mortier et al., 2013), or because methodology can be adapted to mobile systems.

- With respect to mobile observation, a first step has been successfully achieved in the QA4EO phase 1, since real time data processing of AOD is now available. Downward

atmospheric radiance scenario is also performed by the mobile instrument, however efforts have now to be made here to handle sky radiance that together with AOD will go to inversion in AERONET or GRASP.

We also plan to apply GRASP-AOD to high frequency mobile day and night spectral AOD. This is perfectly in line with the QA4EO phase 2 program.

- With respect to stand-alone lidar data processing, and specifically for embedding new fluorescence lidar data in the aerosol retrievals, CNRS-LOA has developed a processing system named AUSTRAL (AUtomatic Server for the TReatment of Atmospheric Lidars) for processing from level 0 to level 2 lidar data. This system has been developed internally by F. Ducos (system and web part) and Q. Hu (scientific functions). It is currently designed for real time lidar data monitoring and visualization, already applicable to a lot of lidar data using the same acquisition card type (LICEL as in EARLINET) and CIMEL for automatic micro-lidar.

Figure 21 : Generic view on AUSTRAL processing framework (source : CNRS-LOA)

To be clear, this does not compete with the ACTRIS/EARLINET–SCC (Single Calculus Chain) since it accounts for advanced lidar functions such fluorescence and also aims for an onboard version for all future autonomous mobile lidar.

6. Conclusions and planned activities for 2022-2025

This brief final section is addressing different aspects of the general activity such as network operation and new methodologies (photometer and lidar), instrumental innovations, data processing and retrievals, campaigns and potential new services to the community.

6.1 Networks

6.1.1 Photometer (AERONET/ACTRIS)

Both in the framework of the ACTRIS implementation, QA4EO and MAPP projects, several metrology activities will be organized and upgraded. First of all the AOD and radiance *traceability with* a regular daytime AOD traceability exercise between GAW PFR and NASA. ACTRIS national investments plan will continue to upgrade the calibration platforms to provide the calibration and maintenance service at the highest level. The MAPP project will

provide an opportunity to obtain and test new led-based calibration source prototypes which will be investigated on the network. In collaboration with MAPP partners and NASA (now associated partners), we expect to much better characterize CIMEL CE318T FOV which could open the way to a strong simplification in the calibration process used within AERONET. At the same time, it is expected to reduce the uncertainty on the radiance which will have a direct impact on the retrieved absorption.

6.1.2 LiDAR (EARLINET/ACTRIS/Meteo France)

CNRS-LOA is coordinating part of the lidar effort in the framework of ACTRIS-France. An important activity will be the real automation of Mie-Raman Lidar in operation in the French ACTRIS-CARS perimeter. Also, in the coming years, new stations and platforms will be set up and operated under the umbrella of ACTRIS-France. New automatic 24/7 elastic-backscatter lidar will be setup at the Amsterdam Island (Indian Ocean, already AERONET), at Lamto (Ivory Coast, already AERONET) and at the observatory of Chacaltaya (Bolivia, already AERONET), very likely in 2023.

Lidar data QC/QA and the centralization of the submission to EARLINET/ACTRIS database for further processing at CNR and at CNRS Data Center will be organized to optimize human resources in each observatory or national facility. A lidar dashboard showing the lidar data from ACTRIS-France perimeter in NRT can be seen at <https://jupyter.icare.univ-lille.fr:5058>. New online functions, visualization will be implemented in 2022.

Finally, all Meteo France *operational* lidar stations distributed in France are now all co-located with AERONET. A close joint cooperation of CNRS-LOA and Meteo France has been established for QC and processing both photometer & lidar data.

6.2 Instruments

As mentioned previously, innovation will continue on the photometer and lidar sides, particularly in the frame of joint private-public partnership. Both for photometer and lidar, LOA and CIMEL will develop new prototypes and increase TRL of existing photometer and lidar prototypes. To develop, contribute further to this innovation program, CNRS-LOA is applying to various national and European calls, searching for funding opportunities to produce a first short series of 1) an industrialized version of Advanced PLASMA (at least 5) and 2) to purchase a small series of ship-borne photometers (at least 5). In the framework of a national project called OBS4CLIM gathering the 3 atmospheric research infrastructure (ACTRIS, ICOS, IAGOS), several new Lidar systems will be purchased and built. A second high power Aerosol-Cloud lidar (with unique Mie-Raman-Fluorescence capabilities) will be built and start operation at LOA-Lille, probably by the end of 2023. The fluorescence capability will enhance the aerosol classification and provide new relevant data for aerosols-clouds interaction studies. One full time research engineer, and at least 3 Ph.D thesis, just started (2021-2024), to work on new lidar systems and their automation (hardware, software, data processing and retrievals). A new high power Aerosol-Cloud lidar (Mie-Raman capability) will be built and start operation at Maïdo-La Réunion, probably by end of 2023 A demonstrator automatic lidar will be set up on TGV that is expected to operate regularly in France.

6.3 Data Processing and Aerosol retrievals

Most have been written in section 5.3. The main plan, in the frame of QA4EO phase 2 will focus on mobile photometer data processing and retrievals, embedding when existing, a lidar companion. The main algorithms are known, but have to be adapted or updated. However, the next step is more to service by implementing a reliable and QC processing chain which is the first direction. The second direction is to develop, in a consistent and traceable manner, a similar onboard processing system. These perspectives fit well the AUSTRAL framework development that is expected to output, in the future, standard files for ACTRIS QC, provide comparison of results with ACTRIS SCC, add new functions (Mie-Raman inversion, aerosol microphysics retrievals, fluorescence, classification), automatic coupling with photometric data in different ways, to improveImprovement of the visual design and ergonomoy.

6.4 Campaign / Data acquisition

- In France, Marion Dufresne will offer opportunities to sample aerosols over several oceans in the coming years, mainly Indian Ocean. A short time campaign including an automatic lidar is under consideration. A demonstrator lidar will be made available for a 3-month test. If the conclusion of this technical feasibility study is positive, then at least one such automatic lidar system must be funded for permanent use. It could be partly funded by the second phase of the MAP-IO program, but complementary financial support will have to be found.

From Summer to Autumn, 2022, one ship-borne photometer from NASA will be set up on a NOAA research vessel, with the help of CNRS-LOA.

In the frame of QA4EO Phase 2, it is expected to purchase a ship-photometer to set it up on a third vessel to be defined (in the list of ACTRIS exploratory platforms or other).

CNRS has contact with CSIRO (Australia) who has potential interest to set up such an instrument on a research vessel.

An automatic lidar will be operated on the French *Polar-Pod* fleet from 2023-2025 around Antarctica. LOA will be in charge of this instrument. This will be a contribution of aerosol/cloud observation in the complex region, and an original support to Cal/Val.

Finally, mobile Aerosols Monitoring System (MAMS, a standard car) from LOA can be deployed during dedicated campaigns, on request for satellite validation or for scientific campaigns. It includes an automatic lidar and a photometer, all measuring during the car's motion.

6.5 New Services

All the previous efforts and coordination aimed at providing reliable data useful for coming space missions validation and all other scientific and technical questions.

Among them, preparation of new services associated with mobile observations. ACTRIS-IMP/H2020 offers a first but very small support to that. QA4EO-phase 1 was supporting this new direction in terms of man-power and this is very important. Support is

requested for this in QA4EO Phase 2 to target the new service. The MAP-IO programme appears to be a good candidate to apply this (instrument is supported by the program).

7. Publications

Here are listed, for End 2019- early 2022 period, the scientific production related to field or specific campaigns involving photometer & Lidar. Publications/Abstracts listed below are from the main staff involved in the project. Additional list of publications of users (using AERONET-LOA calibration services could be provided on request).

Publications (by people directly involved in the project)

- Veselovskii, I., Hu, Q., Goloub, P., Podvin, T., Korenskiy, M., Derimian, Y., Legrand, M. & Castellanos, P. (2020). Variability in lidar-derived particle properties over West Africa due to changes in absorption: towards an understanding. *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 20(11), 6563-6581. [10.5194/acp-20-6563-2020](https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-20-6563-2020)
- Hu, Q., Wang, H., Goloub, P., Li, Z., Veselovskii, I., Podvin, T., Li, K. & Korenskiy, M. (2020). The characterization of Taklamakan dust properties using a multiwavelength Raman polarization lidar in Kashi, China. *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 20(22), 13817-13834. [10.5194/acp-20-13817-2020](https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-20-13817-2020)
- Veselovskii, I., Hu, Q., Goloub, P., Podvin, T., Korenskiy, M., Pujol, O., Dubovik, O., and Lopatin, A.: Combined use of Mie-Raman and fluorescence lidar observations for improving aerosol characterization: feasibility experiment, *Atmos. Meas. Tech. Discuss.*, <https://doi.org/10.5194/amt-2020-291>, 2020
- Veselovskii, I., Hu, Q., Goloub, P., Podvin, T., Choël, M., Visez, N., and Korenskiy, M.: Mie–Raman–fluorescence lidar observations of aerosols during pollen season in the north of France, *Atmos. Meas. Tech.*, 14, 4773–4786, <https://doi.org/10.5194/amt-14-4773-2021>, 2021.
- Torres, B. and Fuertes, D.: Characterization of aerosol size properties from measurements of spectral optical depth: a global validation of the GRASP-AOD code using long-term AERONET data, *Atmos. Meas. Tech.*, 14, 4471–4506, <https://doi.org/10.5194/amt-14-4471-2021>, 2021.
- Popovici, I.E.; Deng, Z.; Goloub, P.; Xia, X.; Chen, H.; Blarel, L.; Podvin, T.; Hao, Y.; Chen, H.; Torres, B.; et al. Mobile On-Road Measurements of Aerosol Optical Properties during MOABAI Campaign in the North China Plain. *Atmosphere* 2022, 13,21. <https://doi.org/10.3390/atmos13010021>

- Hu, Q., Goloub, P., Veselovskii, I., and Podvin, T.: The characterization of long-range transported North American biomass burning plumes: what can a multi-wavelength Mie-Raman- polarization- fluorescence lidar provide ?, *Atmos. Chem. Phys. Discuss.*, 10.5194/acp-2021-971, 2021
- Veselovskii, I., Hu, Q., Ansmann, A., Goloub, P., Podvin, T., and Korenskiy, M.: Fluorescence lidar observations of wildfire smoke inside cirrus: A contribution to smoke-cirrus – interaction research, *Atmos. Chem. Phys. Discuss.* <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-2021-1017>
- Yin Z., A. Ansmann, H. Baars, R. Martin, C. Jimenez, R. Engelmann, P. Seifert, A. Herzog, K. Ohneiser, K. Hanbuch¹, L. Blarel, P. Goloub, G. Dubois, S. Victori, and F. Maupin, Aerosol measurements with shipborne sun-sky-lunar photometer and collocated multiwavelength Raman polarization lidar over the Atlantic Ocean, *AMTD*, <https://doi.org/10.5194/amt-2019-132>, 2019.
- Sieglinde Callewaert, Sophie Vandenbussche, Nicolas Kumps, Arve Kylling, Xiaoxia Shang, Mika Komppula, Philippe Goloub, Martine De Mazière, The Mineral Aerosol Profiling from Infrared Radiances (MAPIR) algorithm: version 4.1 description and validation, *AMTD*, <https://doi.org/10.5194/amt-2019-84>.
- Hu, Q., Goloub, P., Veselovskii, I., Bravo Aranda, J.-A., Popovici, I., Podvin, T., Haefelin M., Lopatin, A., Pietras, C., Huang X., Torres, B. and Chen, C. (2018). A study of long-range transported smoke aerosols in the Upper Troposphere/Lower Stratosphere, *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 19, 1173-1193, 2019, <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-19-1173-2019>
- Torres, B. and Fuertes, D.: Characterisation of aerosol size properties from measurements of spectral optical depth: a global validation of the GRASP-AOD code using long-term AERONET data, *Atmos. Meas. Tech. Discuss.*, <https://doi.org/10.5194/amt-2020-426>, 2020.

Publications in preparation

- De Brito J.F. et al., Extreme heat wave impacts on northern France’s atmospheric dynamics, reactivity and composition: Overview of COBIACC field campaign”, soon submitted to ACP, 2021

Conference / workshop

- Popovici I.E , M. F. Sanchez Barrero P. Goloub, T. Podvin, L. Blarel, G. Dubois, A. Lampionak, L. Proniewski, S. Victori, B. Holben, D. Giles, A. LaRosa, T. Eck, M. Sorokin, J. Schafer, A. Smirnov, A. Sinyuk, I. Slutsker, J. Kraft, J. Campbell, E. Welton, Smoke Observations by LIDAR and Sun Photometer Mobile Measurements during FIREX-AQ Campaign in summer 2019, Smoke symposium, Virtual, Avril 202

- Popovici I.E , M. F. Sanchez Barrero P. Goloub, T. Podvin, L. Blarel, G. Dubois, A. Lapiouak, L. Proniewski, S. Victori, B. Holben, D. Giles, A. LaRosa, T. Eck, M. Sorokin, J. Schafer, A. Smirnov, A. Sinyuk, I. Slutsker, J. Kraft, J. Campbell, E. Welton , Smoke Observations by Lidar and Sun Photometer Mobile Measurements during FIREX-AQ campaign in summer 2019, European Lidar Conference, Virtual, 2020.
- Giles David, Brent Holben, Tom Eck, Ilya Slutsker, Anthony LaRosa, Mikhail Sorokin, Alexander Smirnov, Alexander Sinyuk, Joel Schafer, Jason Kraft, Amy Scully, Philippe Goloub, Thierry Podvin, Luc Blarel, Lelia Proniewski, Ioana Popovici, Gael Dubois, Aliaksandr Lapyonok, FIREX-AQ ER2 – 23 June 2020, AERONET DRAGON Mobile Observations during FIREX-AQ, Williams Flats Fire, Smoke symposium, Virtual, Avril 2020
- Veselovski I., P. Goloub, Hu Q., T. Podvin, Aerosol characterization from Raman and fluorescence lidar measurements, European Lidar Conference, 2020
- Hu Q., P. Goloub, I. Veselovski, T. Podvin, Transported Californian smoke layers over Lille, workshop ACTRIS, November 2020, France
- Chang Y., Q. Hu, P. Goloub Retrieval of aerosol properties from lidar measurements based on the Maximum Likelihood Estimation method, ELC 2021
- Hu Q., P. Goloub, I. Veselovskii, T. Podvin, The study of California smoke in Lille, ELC 2021
- Veselovskii I., Q. Hu, P. Goloub, T. Podvin, A. Ansmann, M. Korenskiy, Application of fluorescence lidar for characterization of smoke particles in upper troposphere and inside cirrus clouds, ELC 2021
- Sanchez M. F, Popovici I, P. Goloub, T. Podvin, L. Blarel, S. Victori, Aerosol properties retrieved from LIDAR and Photometer mobile measurements during FIREX-AQ Campaign in 2019, ELC 2021

Popovici I. E , et al., Performances and evolution of CIMEL CE376 LIDAR, ELC 2021

Internal reporting

- Hu Q., P. Goloub et al. June 2020, Pre-analysis of some column integrated aerosol optical properties, with focus on Spring 2020 COVID-19 period, internal report, LOA.

Internships 2020-2021 LOA

- Chang Y., Hu Q., Goloub P., Dust Aerosol Observation (DAO) campaign: Analysis of aerosol events observed at Kashi site, Master 2 internship, 2020. University de Lille
- Maria Fernanda SANCHEZ BARRERO, Analysis of the Mobile Remote Sensing data from North American FIREX-AQ intensive field campaign, Master 2 internship, 2020. University de Lille

PhD Thesis in preparation at CNRS

- Yuyang Chang : Development of a new technique for measuring the atmospheric profile in aerosols using a Mie-Raman lidar, démarrage en octobre 2020
- Maria F Barrero Sanchez, Développement d'un système intégré autonome temps réel combinant sondage lidar et photométrie automatiques pour la mesure des aérosols, démarrage en février 2021
- Robin Miri, Etude des interactions aérosols-nuages par synergie de mesures Lidar Mie-Raman-Polarisée-Fluorescence, radiomètres MO et IR (2021-2024)
- William Boissière, Développement d'un Lidar Raman-Fluorescence pour l'étude des particules et gaz atmosphériques (2021-2024), U-LILLE

Annex Documents

Annex 1 : Certificate of calibration delivered by ACTRIS-CARS french unit

AERONET-Europe Calibration Sensing Automatic Sun/Sky/Lunar Photometers (CARS-ASP-FR)

Service National d'Observation
PHOTONS/AERONET-EARLINET
Laboratoire d'Optique Atmosphérique
CNRS-Université de Lille
Villeneuve d'Ascq, France

Calibration Certificate

(ACTRIS IMP Transnational Access to CARS-ASP-FR)

Photometer: # 912

Project leader : Peter Hrabčák
Aerological and radiation measurement Center
Slovak Hydrometeorological Institute
Poprad-Ganovce, Slovakia

I, Philippe Goloub, herewith confirm that in the context of ACTRIS Transnational Access the following instrument services were performed at the **CNRS CARS Unit** of the European AERONET Calibration Service Centre:

- Calibration/maintenance of field instrument
- Calibration of reference instrument
- Final functional test
- Calibration update in AERONET database
- Data reprocessing applied
- Data raised to QA level (AERONET level 2)

Project Acronym: AELOA_SK_POP1-22

Calibration date : 04/01/2022

The calibration process of the instrument was carried out

successfully after 1 2 3 calibration process (unit of access).

Standard AERONET Non AERONET user & CIMEL customer Other types of Instrument

The next calibration/maintenance is recommended in about 12 months after the present calibration date.
The PI will have to submit a new TNA application form for that purpose, including an update of the publications.

Important notice to user:

- Daytime AOD are traceable to GAW/PMOD/WRC (OHP Observatory) and AERONET (NASA/Mauna Loa)
- Radiance calibration is traceable with AERONET (NASA/GSFC)

Comments to user:

The calibration procedure was provided free of charge

Villeneuve d'Ascq 20/01/22
Signature of access provider

(P. Goloub)

Reminder: the following acknowledgement sentence is mandatory for all publications: Authors acknowledge AERONET-Europe for providing calibration service. AERONET-Europe is part of ACTRIS-IMP project that received funding from the European Union (H2020-INFRADEV-2018-2020) under Grant Agreement No 871115

<https://www-loa.univ-lille1.fr/photons>
<https://www.actris.eu/Home.aspx> (v 22.04.2021)

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